

Conductometric and Thermochemical Studies in Non-Aqueous Solvents : Part III. Nature of Solutions of Lewis Acids in *n*-Butanol

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Conductometric and thermochemical studies have been carried out to understand the nature of solutions of some Lewis acids in *n*-butanol. Equivalent conductance at different concentrations, molar heats of solutions of Lewis acids, conductometric, thermochemical as well as visual titrations of tertiary bases suggest the solutions to be quite stable and do not undergo solvolysis for fairly long time upto 27°. Relative orders of strength of the Lewis acids and organic tertiary bases have been assigned on the basis of conductance and thermochemical data in *n*-butanol. The mode of ionisation of *n*-butanol

has been fully supported.

A survey of literature reveals that tin (IV) and titanium (IV) chlorides are solvolyzed by alcohols on refluxing.¹⁻⁴ However, stable solvates of boron trifluoride⁵, aluminium⁶, tin (IV)⁷ and antimony (V)⁸ chlorides have been isolated with alcohols at low temperatures and their structures elucidated.⁹⁻¹⁰ The nature of solutions of Lewis acids in *n*-butanol at ordinary temperature is not yet clearly understood. An attempt has been made to study the nature of these solutions in *n*-butanol at room temperature with the help of conductance and thermochemical methods and the results are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

n-Butanol was purified as reported earlier.¹¹ Antimony (V), tin (IV) and arsenic (III) chlorides, tin (IV) bromide and the organic tertiary bases were prepared and/or purified as reported earlier^{12,13}. Germanium (IV) chloride (BDH) was used as such.

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Thermochemical measurements were carried out in an isothermal phase-change calorimeter designed after Dainton *et al.*¹⁴. Diphenyl ether was used as the dilatometric fluid (m.p. 26.9°). The working of the calorimeter and the method for determining the heats of solution and neutralisation have been reported earlier¹². The accuracy of the apparatus is better than $\pm 1\%$

Conductances were measured on Toshniwal Model CL 01/01 precision measuring bridge working at 3 kc/s, using a dip type cell with a cell constant of 0.305 maintained at $25 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lewis acids are freely miscible with *n*-butanol in exothermic reactions and the solutions were prepared in cold. These solutions are highly conducting and the conductance is many times the conductance of either the acids^{15,16} or the solvent¹⁷. Equivalent conductances of the solutions of tin (IV) and antimony (V) chlorides have been measured and plotted against the square root of concentration \sqrt{C} , (Fig. 1) in the range $0.29-8.0 \times 10^{-4}$ moles/litre. It is

evident from the plots that the acids are more ionised at lower concentrations. The conductance of the solutions may be explained by the following reactions taking place simultaneously in solution :

14. F. S. Dainton, J. Diaper, K. J. Ivin and D. R. Sheard, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 1269.

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The solvate of tin (IV) chloride ($\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$) may ionise in two steps giving rise to $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH} \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}^-$ and $(\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O})^{2-}$, the released protons being solvated by *n*-butanol. Equivalent conductance at infinite dilution (λ_0) has been obtained by extrapolation of the curves. The values indicate that antimony (V) chloride is stronger than tin (IV) chloride.

Similarly organic tertiary bases are also miscible with the solvents and give conducting solutions.

The ionic nature of the solutions has been confirmed by conductometric titrations of these acids with α -picoline and triethylamine (Fig. 2). Addition of the acid solution to that of the base in *n*-butanol results in an increase in conductance of the solution till acid/base molar ratio 1 : 1 is reached, where there is a break in the curve. A break corresponding to the molar ratio 1 : 2 in the case of tin (IV) chloride with α -picoline suggests the formation of normal salt and the break at 1 : 1 molar ratio corresponds to the acid salt. The break at the molar ratio 1 : 4 in the case of tin (IV) chloride and triethylamine indicates the formation of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 4\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O} \cdot 4\text{BH}$. However, no such neutralization compound has so far been reported.

FIG 2 CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF LEWIS ACIDS VERSUS BASES IN *n*-BUTANOL AT 25°

Visual titrations of the two Lewis acids against triethylamine, quinoline and α -picoline using methyl red, methyl orange and dimethyl yellow as indicators have also been carried out. The end point is detected by the change in colour from yellow in basic to crimson red, orange red and blood red in slightly acidic solutions.

However, the end points are not so sharp as in the titrations of these bases with protonic acids.¹⁸

The neutralisation reactions may be represented as :

This clearly indicates that the Lewis acids do not undergo solvolysis, as in the event of solvolytic reactions, the end points would have been different depending upon the quantity of hydrochloric acid produced.

Thermochemical Studies : Heats of solution of tin (IV), antimony (V), germanium (IV) and arsenic (III) chlorides and tin (IV) bromide are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Lewis Acid	Heat of solution ($-\Delta H$, kcal/mole)
SbCl ₅	... 33.5 ± 0.2
SnCl ₄	... 30.8 ± 0.2
SnBr ₄	... 20.4 ± 0.2
GeCl ₄	... 9.0 ± 0.05
AsCl ₃	... 7.17 ± 0.09

These values are the mean of four to five values obtained at different concentrations in the range 1.3 to 15.5×10^{-4} mole/litre.

Heat of solution of a Lewis acid in a polar solvent is due to (i) solvate formation, (ii) ionisation of the solvate, and (iii) the solvation of the ions so produced. Relatively smaller heat of solution of germanium (IV) chloride suggests that it is a weaker Lewis acid. Sisler *et al*¹⁹ have observed the failure of germanium (IV) chloride to form addition compounds with ethers. On the basis of physico-chemical studies, Paul and co-workers²⁰ have also shown it to be a weaker Lewis acid in acetone. Arsenic (III) chloride is expected to be a weak Lewis acid because of the presence of a free lone pair of electrons. Enthalpy changes on the dissolution of Lewis acids may be explained on the basis of the equations 1-3.

Heat of solution is a fairly reliable measure of the strength of Lewis acids in a polar solvent.^{12,13} On this basis the Lewis acids may be arranged according to their strength in the following order :

18. R. C. Paul, K. S. Dhindsa, S. C. Ahluwalia and S. P. Narula, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
19. H. H. Sisler, H. H. Batey, B. Pfahler and R. Mattair, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3821.
20. R. C. Paul, R. Kumar, K. S. Dhindsa, S. C. Ahluwalia and S. P. Narula, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 641.

Heats of solution of some organic tertiary bases have also been measured. The values recorded in table II show the maximum variation for four to five measurements in the concentration range 0.8 to 3.0×10^{-3} mole/litre.

TABLE II

Base	Heat of solution ($-\Delta H$, kcal/mole)
Piperidine	... 1.87 ± 0.05
α -picoline	... 0.78 ± 0.02
Pyridine	... Nil
Dimethylaniline	... Slightly endothermic

The strength of these bases in *n*-butanol can be given the following order :

On comparing the heats of solution of any one of the above bases in different alcohols,^{13,21} they may be given the following order of decreasing basicity :

Heats of neutralisation of antimony (V) and tin (IV) chlorides against α -picoline, pyridine and dimethylaniline have been measured and are tabulated along with the reported values of protonic acids :¹⁸

TABLE III

Acid	Heat of Neutralization ($-\Delta H$, kcal/mole) with		
	α -picoline	pyridine	dimethylaniline
SbCl ₅	7.56	7.35*	7.27
SnCl ₄	7.27	7.39*	5.60
H ₂ SO ₄	8.40	8.10	6.70
H ₂ S ₂ O ₇	7.50	7.40	—
H ₂ SO ₄	8.40	8.40	7.60

* As a solid compound separates during the reaction, this value also includes the heat of precipitation.

From the table it is clear that in general the difference of heat of neutralization between the protonic and Lewis acids with the same base varies between 0.5 to 2.0 k.cal/mole which is not significant in view of the absence of data regarding the extent of dissociation of various neutralization compounds.

The heat of neutralization in any solvent is mainly due to the combination of anions and cations characteristic of the solvent. Alcohols are known to ionise as :²²

Since the heat of neutralization is nearly the same with Lewis as well as protonic acids, it may be inferred that both of them protonate the solvent nearly to the same extent. Whereas protonic acids do so directly, the Lewis acids form solvates which, subsequently ionise and protonate the solvent (equations 1–3). Thus the proposed nature of the solutions is supported. Moreover, it can be safely concluded that the Lewis acids used, form stable solutions in *n*-butanol at ordinary temperatures and do not undergo solvolysis.

22. H. A. Laitinen, "Chemical Analysis", McGraw Hill Book Company Inc., London, 1960, p. 60.

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